

Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

The present document (D6.3) outlines the approach, objectives and targets for the communication activities to be implemented in the Horizon Europe funded “Europe Startup Nations Alliance - ESNA” project. The highlights of the communications strategy and goals are:

- Defining the communication objectives, roles and procedures.
- Synchronising communication activities within partner’s institutions.
- The engagement with project stakeholders and audience: the participation in and organisation of events and foreseen publications.
- Supporting the best information flow between all the entities envolved on the project
- Defining de branding and positioning of the project.
- The visual identity and dissemination tools of the project: logo, website, social media, video, leaflet, newsletter and press releases.

Dissemination and communication are cross-cutting activities; therefore, the work is carried out in close cooperation with all the project WPs, in order to receive feedback and contents to be elaborated and used to disseminate and communicate the project externally and publicly. Each project partner has a task and/or efforts to be actively involved in disseminating and communicating the project results using the provided tools and following the defined strategies.

1. Introduction

The purpose of the Communication Strategy is to identify and organize the activities to be carried out to communicate the activities of the ESNA project. It outlines the project's overall approach to external communication. This external communication includes all public communication activities carried out by the project and addressed to the general public of the project. The main objective of communication is to ensure that the project public is proactively informed about the project's current activities and, as a result, its visibility to the public increases steadily over the implementation time.

This report summarizes the strategy and concrete actions to publicize the project, pointing out responsibilities and activities.

the present communication plan attains a critical role. It is the primary document for all questions relating to ESNA's communication. Written at the very beginning of the project, it stays to serve as a source of information for the whole project duration. And as a public deliverable, it is not only made available to the project donor, but also to anyone interested.

Thus, deliverable intends thus, succinctly:

- Ensure that a continuous communication between project partners (internal communication) takes place.
- Ensure that a continuous communication targeted at the project's external audience (external communication) takes place.
- Actively communicate the ESNA project and its outcomes.

In order to improve the project's visibility and increase its impact and reach, and achieve the communication objectives, the ESNA project's Communication Strategy should accomplish the following activities:

1. Create a visible and distinguishable visual identity of the project to make it easily recognisable in a way that all the communicative actions undertaken during the project are traceable.
2. Deploy a media planning to ensure that all the milestones of the project have an accurate broadcasting and reach the targeted audience having the expected impact.
3. Make an intense follow-up of the communication plan deployment, ensuring it's correct functioning and making the necessary corrections when it is needed.
4. Lay out the communication activities among all the partners to ensure a correct deployment of the strategy.
5. Coordinate with external stakeholders, such as related projects, institutions and media to ensure a high outreach of the communication activities

2. Communication Strategy

The main objective of the communication strategy is to promote the ESNA project, its' results and findings to the largest possible audience on all levels (national, European, International). As previously mentioned, the objective of the dissemination strategy is to identify and organize properly the activities needed to achieve these objectives.

The following sections describe the main pillars of the dissemination strategy. Figure 1 presents de communication strategy.

Figure 1 - Communication Strategy outline.

1.1. Subject of communications

The following general subjects of dissemination have been identified up to now:

- ESNA project itself: goals, approach and expected benefits.
- European Startup sector related news.
- Good practices and initiatives in the Startups sector.
- Interviews with stakeholders.
- Share webinars.
- Statistics, facts and figures.
- Press releases.

1.2. Target Audience

For the dissemination of results, there is a distinction between primary and secondary target audiences, as such below:

- **Primary target audiences – Member States:** Primary target audiences are the EU Member States and EEA countries that will join ESNA as members through their national organizations in charge of startup and entrepreneurship policies, thus directly contributing to its activities and benefiting from its results in firsthand, and that as such will be the primary target for all communication and dissemination actions.
- **Secondary target audiences - stakeholders in national startup ecosystems:** As a secondary communication and dissemination target for ESNA actions, there are startups

and scaleups established in the different ecosystems across Europe and that will ultimately benefit from the enhanced frameworks established by the project to examine and change their business offer and models, adopting solutions that increase their competitiveness and that of sectors with whom they are working with, allowing them to grow to a global scale while keeping their decision basis in Europe.

There are some further target groups, however, who could/should benefit from the project activities for their own work. It is regarding the following communities as additional secondary target audiences:

- i) Investment community: National Investment Funds, agencies and programmes, Corporations, Business Angels networks, Seed and Venture capital Funds and firms, Investment firms, and public programmes, that may contribute to, or benefit from, the development of the European startup ecosystem.
- ii) Research sector, from academia and large corporations: the research sector, either from academia or corporations, is vital in the collaboration with startups, and should be informed and engaged in communication actions about the improvement of entrepreneurship framework conditions. It is also a target for data capture.
- iii) Public sector (not directly linked with startup policies): this sector, even if not directly involved in startup ecosystem management, can clearly benefit from the results of startup innovation to improve the quality of public services and, ultimately, better serve populations. Also, data and analytics delivered by the project should help to improve public policy in general, and not only entrepreneurship policies.
- iv) Civil society: These are the ultimate beneficiaries of startup innovation. We will value the right for citizens and groups to participate in and have access to policy making and startups' innovation within our communication activities.

It's contemplated also as dissemination targets all intermediaries who can help to promote and disseminate the results of the project to the primary and secondary beneficiaries listed above. Their interest in the results stems from a mandate to inform about innovation trends; for them, the project and its results and activities are resources – it provides them with information and “content” which they can use in the services they provide to their clientele. These include:

- i) Innovation hubs, knowledge transfer agencies, and regional innovation networks (in particular EEN members) that support businesses in their innovation activity and engaged themselves in creating favourable framework conditions and a positive “innovation culture”. It is part of their daily business to monitor innovation trends and keep themselves up to date; the cases, reports and workshops offered by the project will therefore present a valuable information source and platform for them.
- ii) Researchers from universities and think tanks dealing with entrepreneurship and innovation (policy) issues, e.g., at chairs / institutes for economics, business administration, technology, social sciences and others; as well as private research organizations, non-profit research organizations and research branches of foundations. For them, the project is not only a source of information, but also a platform to interact with and to promote their own research on a European platform.
- iii) Industry associations and federations, in particular their representatives who deal with entrepreneurship and innovation issues (framework conditions, technological developments).

- iv) Other business associations and interest groups, including employees' organizations and unions; employers' organizations and chambers of commerce.
- v) The media, including in particular business and innovation magazines or portals.

1.3. Time of Communication

The correct timing of dissemination of project activities and results can mean a difference between success and failure in terms of European-wide reach and creating a lasting impact. It is important to communicate about the project and its activities throughout the lifetime, however, to effectively distribute the limited resources, it is crucial to define the stages, at which the objective, content and message delivered will be different and dependent on the stage of the project.

ESNA wish to drive and foster networking between national public bodies in charge of entrepreneurship policies (primary target), but also startups, public sector, academia, businesses, entrepreneurs and civil society (secondary targets). The method followed (AIDA) is outlined below:

- A-ttention (Awareness): attract the attention of the stakeholders and keep raising awareness through a website updates/briefings/notes of events. Awareness does not come from website updates though, it must come from outreach via multipliers.
- I-nterest: raise stakeholder interest by focusing on and demonstrating advantages and benefits of using ESNA services and data for enhancing national ecosystem governance and framework conditions.
- D-esire: convince stakeholders that using ESNA services will enhance national framework conditions and eventually increase both national and EU competitiveness.
- A-ction: lead stakeholders towards taking action – eventually resulting in increased framework conditions for startup and scaleups growth within their countries.

What we propose to add to this model is:

S-ustain: the interest of the people on the alliance (and on SNS) must be sustained, so they keep coming back and contribute to the growth of the ESNA. Sustainability and scalability are key aspects that must be kept in mind from the beginning onward as a fundamental pillar of all the work

1.4. Communication tools and channels

To reach each target group defined successfully and efficiently, a variety of communication tools and channels will be employed by the ESNA project. Thus, activities and materials will have two roles: inform on the one hand and create desire and trigger action on the other hand.

In order to reach at a cost-effective level the audiences defined, the guiding principle in choosing tools and distribution channels is simple: going where the audiences are present, including conferences, workshops, meetups and camps related to open innovation and entrepreneurship.

These are, for instance, the Web Summit in Lisbon or other high-profile events for startups and innovation, that will be complemented by web-based socialization platforms.

ESNA will establish a portfolio of social media with the aim of communicating with specific target groups across Europe and beyond, including a YouTube video-sharing playlist via the project's channels, Twitter for policy engagement, and a Flickr gallery of images. A dedicated LinkedIn page will be created to connect professionals from different backgrounds and areas of expertise related to entrepreneurship, from startups to policymakers. Through social media, ESNA will be linked to other initiatives, journalists, and EU/national research projects to maximize outreach.

Following are presented a clear definition of each of these tools and communication channels to be used within the scope of the ESNA project.

Website

ESNA website (<https://esnalliance.eu/>) is already and will be the main interface for communication to the public, serving as a primary source of information regarding ESNA's objectives, progress and outcomes with the aim of organizing the project information into a unified source of visitor's knowledge. According to the progress of the project, the content of the website will be continuously extended and updated.

To maximize its visibility, free or affordable methods to increase page ranking on search engines will be used. The web will include information of the project and the possibility to contact with project partners for interested stakeholders. Interested parties will have the possibility to register to receive updated information and networking opportunities.

The website is aimed to reach all primary and secondary audiences of the ESNA project. The main communication objectives of the ESNA website are:

- To provide relevant and updated information to a wide audience.
- To ensure information is provided in an accessible and usable manner.
- To be a common documentation base for all the partners, containing the main project documentation and deliverables.

Social Media Networking

Nowadays, social media plays a very important role in reaching specific target audiences and disseminating various information towards them. Thus, in order to reach its target audience and establish two-way communication channels, the presence of the ESNA project on social media will be encouraged. This is important to increase the project's visibility and build an audience.

<https://twitter.com/esnalliance>

@ESNAlliance

Twitter will be used for a big scale bidirectional communication, with all the audience present on this social media, but focusing on a technical audience from the Startups area. This social media will be crucial on Events, Conferences or Workshops to broadcast ESNA role on these scenarios and attract followers through real time information. The type of content will be, mostly, infographics, videos, links, news or documents.

As it is spread a new message on Twitter, it is possible to connect and engage with new interested, network with the partners, and identify influencers. It's also possible to use it as a way to communicate with target groups, get informal feedback, and interact with them.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/esnalliance/>

LinkedIn is a professional social network and will be used to reach a business and scientific audience. Will be the scenario to share news and articles about the progress and outcomes of the project. The objective is to disseminate the progress of the project among the stakeholders, attracting knowledge and generate awareness. The type of message will be Infographics, pictures, videos, links, news or documents.

Project brochures and other materials

To contribute to the promotion and communication of the project objectives, its outcomes, a number of brochures, videos, presentations, leaflets, posters, rol-ups ups and other materials will be produced.

The brochure will be able to be distributed in printed form (handed out at conferences or other events) or in electronic version (PDF file) and will be also downloadable from the project website.

There will be short Project presentations, describing the objectives and the main achieved results for presenting the project in different forums, such as internal presentations inside of the partners, presentations at events/conferences, visits with clients, etc.

It will be produced project related videos, to communicate the project's vision, objectives, and results. These presentations will be accessible from the website and could be uploaded in YouTube.

Project Newsletters

To increase the impact of the project there will be a newsletter containing the main news and information about the project. ESNA will ensure the existence of enough materials to be included in the Newsletter and ask other consortium members for their partners.

In this sense, an external newsletter will be issued each semester (from M6) to present the latest results of the projects, success stories, news from the partners, upcoming events, events where project consortium members assist, etc.

The newsletter will be defined according to the European legislation in this sense, and it will be forwarded to all the subscribers who decide to do so through the website, e-mail or other media such as recommendation of the consortium members.

National and international events and workshops

ESNA will assist to different congresses, conferences and workshops and according to the event agenda, they should lead debates, carry out project-related speeches and/or workshops, contact with stakeholders and market leaders or assist to chats and debates to contribute or learn about the actual opinions and tendencies in the industry.

Table below provides a provisional list of the events that the ESNA will take part in, presenting project' results and the next steps.

Announcement of the different workshops/events will be done through all the available channels (Webside, Twitter, LinkedIn, ESNA newsletter) to reach the maximum audience as possible.

Table 1 – List of events.

Event name	Description	Location	Date
ESNA Forum	Annual meeting for high level governmental representation	Lisbon@Web Summit	Nov 3rd
SME Assembly envoy*	To be determined	Prague	28-30 Nov
Slush*	To be determined	Finland	17.18 ov

*to be confirmed

Media and Social Media coverage

Media coverage outside the social media outlets, described earlier, is expected to occur in the duration of ESNA project through both digital and traditional means (newspapers, magazines, news outlets, podcasts, etc.). Through this coverage, it is expected to spread the information about the project to general public, such as planned activities, deliverables and more. Each partner will coordinate the press relations in their respective countries.

Open Access and Research Data Management

A central aim of ESNA is to provide benefit to its member states and their entrepreneurial ecosystems via open access and sharing of data and knowledge. Special emphasis will be placed on fostering open access to the data and analysis on the Digital Platform. All produced results and documents (reports) will be accessible through this open access portal and all publications will be granted open access according to publisher and law regulations as set out in the Grant Agreement.

Depending on the nature of the publication, the articles will be made available immediately through open access publishing ('gold' open access) or within a period of 6 months through self-archiving ('green' open access).

ESNA is already considering various Open Access policies: supporting authors in retaining their rights to provide access to published articles, providing institutional repositories (green open access), and making the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication available to OpenAIRE. Other means include finding suitable repositories via OpenAIRE, the Registry of Open Access Repositories, and the Directory of Open Access Repositories. One of the main initiatives of ESNA is to engage with multiple stakeholders and develop an open-source platform with tools and knowledge available to all. ESNA knowledge management and protection strategy aims to be as open as possible to achieve maximum impact of the project results, so the default ruling is that results will be public. The ruling will be different where this is explicitly required by the legitimate explicit interests of data owners (national ecosystems).

3. Communication Management

ESNA will act as Communication and Dissemination Manager of the project, coordinating and supervising all the dissemination activities. This role will be conducted in close cooperation with the other project's partners and also with Inova+, an entity contracted to support the planning and communication of the project.

In order to maximize the project's output, all project partners are constantly asked to contribute to the implementation of all communication and dissemination activities; continuous input from all partners is therefore required throughout the entire project period.

Project partners will be invited to plan and implement concrete communication activities: to make sure the project logo and a news-item figures on their website, that their organisation is engaged on social media with the project, that they distribute project flyers and newsletters, contribute with either written articles or ideas for content for the website, and provide event/publication information.

All partners will report their project-related communication and dissemination activities in the file created for dissemination reporting (Dissemination Log) available on the project repository, including information on events they attended and those they are planning to attend.

To ensure efficient use of the communication and dissemination tools, as well as resource allocation between the partners, a dissemination schedule will be created. LinkedIn, being a social media outlet targeted primarily towards professionals, will post relevant information in the mornings, as it is the peak time of following up with the current trends in various industries. As Twitter is a platform primarily focused on the free (leisure) time of its users, relevant information about the project will be shared during the evenings and/or weekends. It is important to note that the dynamics of social media usage might change during the lifetime of the project and, if necessary, adjustments to the dissemination schedules will be made to ensure widespread reach of the audience.

Inside the website of the project, sections will be revised on a regular basis to make sure the news, project results and other relevant matters are up to date and relevant to its viewers. Furthermore, the ESNA will regularly analyse the user experience (UX) of the website and adjust it, if necessary, to best guide newly interested visitors.

Communication strategy and content of the ESNA can be broken down into 3 distinctive categories, which are:

- News: relevant activities, milestones, news articles, etc. of the project.
- Future conferences/events that will be attended by partners: collection of necessary preliminary information about events for dissemination via social media and/or other channels.
- Summary of conferences/events that already happened: collection of information about past events to generate content for different communication channels.

4. Work Plan

This section describes the main dissemination and communication activities planned for the project. Some of these activities have already been carried out while most of them are in progress.

3.1. Logo design and visual identity

Having a unique logo of the project and visual identity ensure that project outputs are consistent, easily recognizable and trackable in the vast exchange of information that is happening online. For this step, consortium developed key aspects and ideas it aimed to represent through the below shown logo.

Figure 2 – Project's logo.

The logo is constituted by the junction of four basic geometric shapes: squares, circles, triangles, creating the idea of unity. By applying one of the initials letters into each basic shape, it's conveyed the metaphor of entrepreneurship: the creation or extraction of value. The initials' union conveys the Alliance and the triangle / arrow shape translates the start-up context and its acceleration. The Brand's concept resides in its modularity. The 4 initials can work in different ways. This diversity conveys economic growth, innovation and dynamism in a digital world. The link to Europe is made by the Brand's colors: Pantones Reflex Blue and Yellow, of the Europe's Flag.

The ESNA's project logo will be used in the following cases:

- All documents developed within the framework of the ESNA project and documents to be submitted to the granting authority (e.g. deliverables).
- ESNA website.
- Communication to the public about upcoming activities, events, presentation of results and other relevant information.
- Presentations to be used for communication and dissemination of the project activities, results and other relevant information within the framework of the ESNA project.

To ensure a coherent and professional use of the projects' visual identity, in turn maximizing the impact of the project towards the audience, various templates with the ESNA brand have been prepared. In case of such event, the partner will express the need for addition of a new template, to which the consortium will follow the guidelines, set in this brand book.

The following templates have been created to meet the current and possible future needs of the consortium within the framework of the ESNA project:

- Power Point presentation template, containing the ESNA logo and EU flag, indication of WP, partner organization, place and time of the event. This template will be used by all partners in their relevant presentations, events and other uses.
- A4 Microsoft Word template, using the header and footer areas of the document to showcase the relevant information, as well as logos.

3.2. Implementation and update of Website

The ESNA website is already in operation and aggregates all the information related to the project. The content published in ESNA website will be connected directly with other social media outlets, used by the project's partners and aligned to keep consistent branding and communication.

Google analytics tool will be employed to ensure efficient use of project resources and that the content published on the website is informative, as well as attractive to the general public. Said tools will also act as a quality assurance, as Google Analytics tools are able to show the current and historic visits of the website, heatmap, conversion, geographical location, duration of the stay and other relevant statistics.

The website is divided into the following sections:

- Homepage: on this first page, an institutional video of the project is presented, where the challenge that the project intends to respond to, its state of the art and the general objectives are mentioned. The "Press Release" and links to the social networks Twitter and LinkedIn are also presented.
- About: this section contains the general overview of the project, including background information, objectives and other related information.
- News: in line with the information, shared through social media outlets, this section will have up-to-date articles and new posts about the project activities, published results and other relevant actions within the framework of the ESNA project
- Contact: a final section that provides the option of being able to send a message to the ESNA's partners.

3.3. Social Networks

Twitter and LinkedIn accounts for the ESNA project have been already created and will be used to publish announcement and relevant information of the project. Official Twitter/LinkedIn accounts and groups will be joined to raise awareness among interested stakeholders.

Arthur Jordão (ESNA) will be responsible to oversee project's social media activities.

3.4. Preparation of dissemination materials

Publications and dissemination materials will help to publicize the project, providing a communication channel through which concrete information can be conveyed to the public.

Thus, from the beginning of the project, various publications and dissemination materials will be created and made openly available to promote the project, raise its awareness both digitally

and physically. Through these materials, specific information and message about the project will be conveyed to the public.

An introductory brochure, summarizing the project, its' consortium, objectives and planned activities will be created. The second brochure will be created in the end of the project, to summarise the results produced. Both brochures will be made publicly available on ESNA, where they can be downloaded digitally and used for further dissemination.

Throughout the duration of the project, 4 leaflets and infographics will be created, where various project results will be presented.

5. Key Performance Indicators for Monitoring

Output and impact of communication activities are measured through a bundle of indicators, which will be used for monitoring these activities. Table 2 and 3 present the key performance indicators.

Table 2 – Communication Key Performance Indicators and Targets.

ESNA Outputs and KPI	Stakeholders Group	Targets	
		2023	2024
Digital Platform (# of visits per year)	Members and Entrepreneurship community	1 000	2 000
Twitter (# of followers per year)	All	750	1 500
LinkedIn (# of followers per year)	All	750	1 500
Press Releases	Media / Journalists	3	3
Web site traffic (# of website visits per year)	All	3 000	4 000
Project Leaflet/Flyer (# of flyers distributed)	Policy makers	250	250
Event Participation (# of attendees)	All	75	300